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Situational Management and Leadership

On May 9 and 10, 2024, the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts hosted the VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference for Students and Young Scientists, “Situational Management and Leadership: Theory, History, Culture, and Art of Management”, organized by the Department of Fashion and Show Business¹.

The event gathered 105 students and young scientists from 12 higher education institutions in Ukraine, which offer programs in “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”, including European University, Kyiv University of Culture, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Rivne State University of Humanities, Sumy State University, and others.

The conference united participants in discussions on pressing issues across various thematic areas: the theory and history of situational management; global culture and the art of situational management; leadership and social progress; leadership qualities and methods of their development; the culture, social adequacy, and responsibility of leaders; psycho-pedagogical technologies for forming charismatic leaders; and leadership and the art of situational management in the socio-cultural sphere.

The aim of the VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference was to create a platform for discussing and analyzing current problems of situational management and leadership in the modern world, as well as to seek

¹ Retrieved from <https://knukim.edu.ua/sytuaczijnjy-menedzhment-i-liderstvo-2/>

new ideas, solutions, and approaches to addressing these issues. The conference aimed to generate new knowledge and understanding in the field of situational management and leadership, while also stimulating further research and development in this important area of management.

The VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference was opened by the head of the organizing committee, The Scientific Director of the “Social and Cultural Activity Management” program, Doctor Habilitatus, Professor, and Academician of the International Personnel Academy Yaroslav Martynyshyn. He noted that for a manager, being a leader means acting in a way that competitive situations, in which they constantly find themselves, develop to their advantage or in a desired direction: “The ability to grasp the situation, see the hidden driving forces, understand people, and select the “springs” that set the strength and direction of the situation's development requires much more from an individual than just having the qualifications of a specialist. They must possess a set of certain individual personal leadership qualities, such as the ability to deeply penetrate the essence of different situations, notice and understand the unseen elements within them, and intuitively predict their development. The ability to deviate from traditional thinking patterns, go beyond logic and the visible, and think not only logically but also emotionally and intuitively. The capacity for constant change, differentiation, generating fundamentally new, unconventional ideas, and bringing them to concrete practical results in the form of various attractive things. All this makes an individual a leader and a successful manager”.

The Head of the Department of Fashion and Show Business, Doctor of Habilitatus, Professor Olena Khlystun, addressed all participants with a welcoming speech: “Leadership is a historically formed need of people to organize their activities, and there is an objective need for leadership in society. Can leadership be inherent in any individual, or is it the fate of only a chosen few? Perhaps, leadership is inherent in human nature from birth? Or is it formed as a result of the influence of the surrounding reality? If so, how are leadership qualities formed? These questions, which have troubled people for ages, remain relevant today. I hope they will be actively discussed by students and young scientists at our traditional annual conference. I wish all participants successful, fruitful, and enlightening cooperation, pleasant and productive scientific communication, and creative success”.

The welcoming address at the conference was also given by Professor Serhii Vytkaľov from Rivne State University of Humanities, Associate Professor Larysa Butko from Kremenčuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Associate Professor Yuliia Tymchenko from Kyiv University of Culture, and other senior colleagues present at the conference. Their expert opinions and academic experience complemented the general discussion and inspired participants to a deeper and more meaningful examination of future topics.

Over a hundred scholars registered to participate in the conference, underscoring the significance and relevance of the conference theme and highlighting a wide interest in contemporary approaches to management and leadership. This facilitated an atmosphere of active idea and experience exchange, ensuring a diversity of perspectives on the outlined issues.

The responsibility of chairing the meeting was entrusted to me, Arsenii Pushmin, a Graduate Student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. The organizing committee believed this would foster engaging discussions and a productive exchange of ideas between students and young scientists.

Participants had the opportunity to present their research, express their views, and find common solutions to contemporary challenges faced by managers and leaders. These discussions allowed participants to deepen their knowledge, share experiences and ideas, and discover new approaches to addressing modern challenges in the field of management and leadership. The Organizing Committee recognized several participants' presentations as the best.

Arsenii Pushmin, a graduate student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “The Importance and Features of Digital Management in the Art and Music Industry”. His research and analysis offered new approaches and solutions to improving management in the art and music industry in the digital age.

Oleksandr Alieksieiev, a graduate student at the National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, presented a report on “Forming a Leadership Civic Position among University Students: An Inclusive Decision-Making Approach”. His presentation examined various methods and strategies that can be used to develop a leadership civic position in students and support their participation in public life.

Daria Rud, a student at the National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, presented a report on “The Features of Leadership and Situational Management in the Socio-Cultural Sphere”. Her presentation explored the specifics of management in the socio-cultural sphere, highlighting the main challenges and opportunities faced by leaders and managers in this field.

Valeriia Laktionova, a graduate student at Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, presented a report on “PR Activities of Organizations in the Socio-Cultural Sphere”. Her presentation provided conference participants with valuable insights and knowledge on the importance of effective PR activities for the development and promotion of socio-cultural projects and organizations.

Vira Sarnavska, a student at Rivne State University of Humanities, presented her report on “Regional Cultural Practices: The Example of a New Type of Museum”. In her presentation, she analyzed the impact of regional cultural features on the formation and development of museums, as well as their role in preserving and promoting cultural heritage.

Tetiana Stepanova, a postgraduate student at European University, presented her report on “Cultural Diplomacy and Cross-Cultural Management in International Relations”. Her report was based on a comprehensive analysis of current theories and practices in the field of international relations, cross-cultural management, cultural diplomacy, as well as her own research and experience in this area.

Oleksandr Darovanets, an assistant at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Leadership During Military Conflict: Cultural Adaptation, Ethical Challenges, and Social Responsibility”. In his presentation, he examined the role and characteristics of leadership in the context of military conflict, focusing on effective strategies and approaches that can be used by leaders in crisis situations to minimize negative impacts.

Iлона Okhrimenko, a student at Sumy State University, presented a report on “Theoretical Foundations of Situational Management in Socio-Cultural Projects”. In her presentation, she highlighted the key aspects of situational management, providing a detailed overview of the theoretical foundations of this approach, including its principles, methods, and tools.

Daria Nemchenko, a student at Kyiv University of Culture, presented a report on “The Role of a Leader in Enhancing Team Performance”. In her presentation, she emphasized the importance of a leader's role in creating an atmosphere of trust, motivation, and interaction within the team, as well as in managing conflicts and achieving common goals.

Iryna Odiahailo, a student at the National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, presented a report on “Cultural Behavior of a Leader in Society”. In her presentation, she analyzed how cultural values, traditions, and norms influence leadership styles and methods, as well as relationships with the team and the success of achieving goals.

Tetiana Samardak, a graduate student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Leadership Qualities and Methods of Their Development: Innovative Approaches to Leadership Training”. Her report was based on a comprehensive analysis of modern approaches to developing leadership qualities and her own experience researching this topic.

Victoriia Reshetylo, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “The Specifics of Personnel Management Systems in Show Business Organizations”. In her presentation, she examined the specific requirements for staff in such organizations, as well as methods and approaches to managing them, considering the unique aspects of working in a creative and dynamic environment.

Oleksandr Bohuslavskyy, a graduate student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “The Impact of Leadership on the Formation and Development of Organizational Culture in Public Administration”. He analyzed which leadership qualities and methods can contribute

to creating a favorable organizational atmosphere, as well as how they affect staff motivation and team efficiency.

Anna Tsyndrenko, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Leadership Qualities and Ways to Develop Them”. In her presentation, she discussed the main qualities that a successful leader should possess, as well as methods and strategies for developing them.

Yevheniia Zasenکو, a student at the National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, presented a report on “Branding Features in Turbulent Environmental Conditions”. In her presentation, she discussed branding methods and strategies that can help companies adapt to changing market conditions, maintain competitiveness, and strengthen their market position.

Daria Kozub, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Leadership Qualities and Methods for Their Development in Managers of Music Labels in Ukraine”. In her presentation, she analyzed the impact of leadership on the development and success of music projects, and examined various approaches and methods for developing leadership qualities in managers of music companies.

Olena Zhylenko, a postgraduate student at Sumy State University, presented a report on “Virtualization of the “Self” in the Modern Information Space”. In her presentation, she explored the phenomenon of personality virtualization in the context of modern information technologies and digital culture.

Yana Bahmet, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Technologies for Forming Charismatic Leaders”. In her presentation, she analyzed the key characteristics of charismatic leaders, their ability to inspire and motivate others, and effective communication strategies.

Anastasiia Antonenko, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Trends and Prospects in Ukraine's Modern Media Space”. In her presentation, she explored the main directions of media industry development in Ukraine and the current trends affecting the formation of the country's information environment.

Olha Ksenzhenko, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Product Placement as an Investment in Film Production”. In her presentation, she examined various aspects of product placement, including its impact on the audience, the effectiveness of marketing strategies, and the financial aspects of incorporating brands into films.

Oleksandr Martynenko, a graduate student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Key Aspects of Effective Personnel Motivation”. In his presentation, he discussed both material and non-material incentives, as well as the psychological and social factors that influence staff motivation.

Yana Li, a student at Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, presented a report on “Types and Directions of Rebranding as a Strategic Tool”. In her presentation, she examined the strategic tasks addressed through rebranding, potential changes to corporate identity, and the marketing strategies used to successfully implement the rebranding process.

Vladyslav Zhosonar, a student at the National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, presented a report on “Leadership Qualities and Methods for Their Development”. The report was based on an extensive analysis of modern leadership concepts and practical methods for developing leadership skills.

One of the key discussion areas was how situational management can help organizations adapt to rapidly changing environments, effectively respond to challenges, and maximize potential. Additionally, issues of culture and the art of management were addressed. Participants shared their insights on how cultural characteristics and values influence leadership style and corporate culture. They discussed methods for building effective team dynamics and creating an environment that stimulates the development of employees' creative potential. Special attention was paid to the historical aspect, as understanding the history of management allows for a better comprehension of contemporary challenges and trends. Scholars analyzed historical examples of leadership and management, drawing lessons from the past to apply them in the present.

The conference also served as a platform for discussing the practical aspects of management and leadership. Participants shared their experiences in solving real-world problems, discussing best practices in project management, team management, and change management. Young scholars emphasized the need to develop leadership qualities in the training of student managers, ensuring their future success in various business situations.

Following an intense exchange of experiences, the conference left a lasting impression on all participants. They gained not only new knowledge and ideas but also inspiration for further development in the field of management and leadership. The VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists became a significant event that enriches the Ukrainian academic and business community and encourages innovative approaches to management in the modern world.

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